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Newmark's Procedures in Persian Translation of Golding's *Lord of the Flies*

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ABSTRACT

Numerous frameworks and procedures have been proposed for translation. In this regard, the Newmark's proposed procedures have been widely discussed in translation studies. Yet, few studies have ever applied his procedures simultaneously for describing and assessing translations. This paper is an attempt to compare the translation procedures used in two Persian translations of Golding's *Lord of the Flies* by Rafiee and Mansoori based on Newmark's translation procedures. The main question is if the translator's procedures can be described and assessed by Newmark's framework or not. To do so, first, some chapters of the English novel were randomly selected, and then, they were compared with their corresponding parts in the Persian translations. Then, comparisons were classified and analyzed in terms of transliteration, shift, synonymy, modulation, addition, omission, as well as mistranslation to find out which procedures were used more by the two translators, and to show the extent of the mistranslated items in the two translations. The results showed that Newmark's procedures are nearly comprehensive and worked well for translating and assessing the translation of a literary work.

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1. Introduction

Translation scholars hold different attitudes toward the essence and role of translation. Researchers in the field of translation studies believe that translation is an extraordinarily broad notion which can be understood as a process, as a product, or as an act of transferring the written texts (Shuttleworth&Cowie, 1997, 2004; Bell; 1991; Hatim and Munday, 2004). Some scholars believe that translation is an expression of what has been said in SL into TL by preserving semantic and stylistic equivalence (Bell, 1991; Hatim and Munday, 2004; Munday, 2001; Larson, 1998; Catford, 1965).

Translation has been regarded as a multi-faceted phenomenon by many scholars. Larson (1998) believes that translation contains not only the text, but also the cultural context. Having discussed idiomatic translation, he maintains that idiomatic translation uses the natural forms of the TT in both grammatical and lexical aspects, and do not sound like a translation, rather, it sounds like an original writing in the TL.

Despite its advantages, idiomatic translation has its own deficiencies. Newmark (1988) explains that idiomatic translation transfers the SL meaning but sometimes changes the meaning a little by using daily conversations or idioms. Newmark (1988) states that SL forms are usually converted to their nearest TL equivalents, but lexical words are singly translated out of context. His idea about literal translation is similar to Catford's idea because both of them state that in literal translation, SL words are translated one by one, TL grammar is perceived as natural TL grammar, and the TL conveys a meaning similar to that of the SL.

Larson (1998) believes that a good translator tries to translate idiomatically, but he adds that consistency in idiomatic or literal translation is really difficult in practice, as actual translations are often a mixture of literal and idiomatic forms of language. According to Larson, form-based translations or word for word translations attempt to follow the form of the SL and are called literal translation. Larson believes that this kind of translation is effective for those who learn or study the original meaning of the SL. Similarly, Catford (1965) says that literal translation is nearly like word for word translation, but the form of the TL is based on the grammar of the TL.

Due to its complexity and multifacetedness, Different definitions have been proposed for translation. Some scholars define translation as a process of replacing or substituting a textual material in SL by a textual equivalent in TL (Catford 1965; Savory, 1969; Nida& Taber, 1969; Pinchuck. 1977; Newmark, 1988; House 2001).

On the other hand, Nida and Taber (1969) emphasize that the primary aim of the translator should be the reproduction of the closest natural equivalent of the SL message, first based on the meaning and then, based on the style. Their definition of translation is different from that of Newmark (1988) who defines translation as rendering the meaning of a text into another language based on the original writer's intent. Scholars such as Newmark (1988) believe that translation is a change of linguistic form, and a translator should be well acquainted with lexicon, grammar and culture of the SL and TL to be able to analyze the ST and determine its meaning (also see Larson, 1998).

As opposed to Newmark, Bassenett (1991) says that rendering a SL into TL is

called translation to the extent that the surface meanings of both languages are nearly similar, and the SL structures are preserved as closely as possible but the TL structures are not distorted too. Like Bassnett, Robinson (1997) considers translator as learner and translation as an intelligent activity which involves the complex processes of conscious and unconscious learning and requires creative problem-solving in novel textual and cultural conditions.

1.1 The Role of Culture in Translation

The notion of translation has always been intermingled with culture, especially after the 1970s. It is a widely recognized fact that culture is a crucial part of translation (Newmark, 1988; Bassnett, 1997; Robinson, 1997; House, 2009). Yet, Newmark (2001) explains that although some scholars see culture as the essence of translation, he himself considers it as the greatest obstacle to translation, at least for achieving an accurate translation. In spite of that, there is an inseparable relation between culture and language and cultural factors are transferred through language from one culture to another (Ivir, 1987; Hermans, 1999). The role of culture is so important that scholars like Armstrong (2005) believe that just a bilingual and bicultural translator is able to carry out a complete translation.

Nida (1964) also believes that translation problems vary depending on the cultural and linguistic gap between the two or more languages. He maintains that both linguistic and cultural differences between the SL and the TL are equally important, and concludes that cultural differences may cause more severe problems for the translator than do linguistic differences. In this regard, Venuti (1995) notes that translation is a process of looking for similarities between languages and cultures,

especially similar messages and formal techniques, however, it does this because it permanently confronts dissimilarities. Venuti adds that translation should never remove these similarities completely; rather, it should show the cultural differences. He mentions that a translation strategy based on an aesthetic of discontinuity can show the differences in the best way; it can show the gains and losses in the translation process and the unbridgeable cultural gaps.

It is believed that translation involves at least two languages and two cultures (Toury, 1978; Bassnett, 1980). This shows that translators are permanently faced with the problem of treating the cultural aspects implicit in the ST and finding the most appropriate technique for conveying these aspects in the TL in a successful way. Newmark (1988) considers culture as the way of life and its manifestations that are peculiar to a community; he says that cultures use languages for expressing their specific features. In contrast to Vermeer's (1989) viewpoint that says language is a component of a culture, Newmark (1988) believes that language is not a part or feature of culture. Newmark explains that Vermeer's stance shows impossibility of translating whereas translating the SL into an appropriate form of the TL is a part of translator's role in the transcultural communication. Hatim and Mason (1997) similarly consider translation as an act of communication which breaks cultural and linguistic boundaries, as an act of communication.

1.2 Translation Procedures

Translation scholars have widely discussed translation strategies, especially the strategies used in rendering cultural elements. Krings (1986) defines translation strategy as the potentially conscious plans which translator considers for solving

translation problems (Kring, 1986; Loescher, 1991). Newmark (1988) suggests a list of translation procedures which consists of Transference, naturalization, cultural equivalent, functional equivalent, descriptive equivalent, componential analysis, synonymy, through translation, shifts or transposition, modulation, recognized translation, compensation, expansion, paraphrase, omission, couplets, and notes.

Translators use different procedures of translation. Nida (1964) proposes two kinds of translation procedures: technical and organizational. Technical procedures consist of analyzing the respective SL and TL, careful studying of the SL text, and determining the appropriate equivalents. On the other hand, the organizational procedures involve the general organization of a work by a single translator or by a committee, and they are applied to all types of translating, but there are different procedural problems.

On the other hand, Vinay and Darbelnet (1976, in Munday, 2001) enumerate seven translation procedures:

Borrowing: transferring the SL word directly to the TL.

Calque: a special kind of borrowing. The SL expression or structure is literally transferred.

Literal translation: word-for-word translation, common between languages of the same family and culture.

Transposition: changing one part of speech for another without changing the sense.

Modulation: changing the viewpoint and semantics of the SL.

Equivalence: describing the same situation by different stylistic or structural means especially in translating proverbs and idioms.

Adaptation: changing the cultural reference when a situation in the source culture does not exist in the target culture.

Considering the above procedures, it might be stated that the first four procedures mostly deal with linguistic aspects of translation and the structural differences between two languages while the last three procedures mainly focus on transferring the cultural aspects of language.

Newmark (1988) differentiate between translation methods and translation procedures and states that translation methods are related to whole texts, however, translation procedures are applied for sentences and the smaller units of language. Then, he introduces the following eight methods of translation on the basis of language used to emphasize either SL or TL:

Table 1: Newmark's Diagram of Translation Methods

SL Emphasis	TL Emphasis
Word-for-word Translation	Adaptation
Literal Translation	Free Translation
Faithful Translation	Idiomatic Translation
Semantic Translation	Communicative Translation

According to Newmark, the translation methods that emphasize on the SL include:

1. **Word-for-word translation:** preserving SL word order and translating the words singly by their most common meanings with no regard for context. Cultural words are literally translated. This method is mainly used to understand the mechanics of the SL or to interpret a difficult text as a pre-translation process.

2. **Literal translation:** converting the SL grammatical constructions to their nearest TL equivalents and translating the lexical words again singly, with no regard for context.

3. **Faithful translation:** producing the precise contextual meaning of the ST with regard for constraints of the TL grammatical

structures. Using this method, the degree of grammatical and lexical abnormality in translation is maintained and cultural words are transferred. Also, translator tries to be completely faithful to the original writer's intent and text realization.

4. Semantic translation: differing from faithful translation only in considering the aesthetic value of the ST.

On the other hand, the translation methods that emphasize on the TL include:

1. Adaptation: the freest form of translation used mainly for dramas (comedies) and poetry by preserving the themes, characters and plots and converting the SL culture to the TL culture. The text is rewritten.

2. Free translation: producing the TT without preserving the style, form, or content of the ST.

3. Idiomatic translation: reproducing the SL message and distorting nuances of meaning by preferring colloquialisms and idioms that don't exist in the ST.

4. Communicative translation: rendering the precise contextual meaning of the ST in way that both content and form are comprehensible to the audience.

1.3 Purpose and Significance of the Study

An appropriate translation procedure can be an important guarantee for the quality of a literary translation. It seems that translating, and investigating translations based on the Newmark's procedures are very useful for the literary translators because these procedures are comprehensive and show the losses and gains in translation. It is hoped that this study will provide further explanation on translation especially on the procedures proposed by Newmark.

The translation from English into Persian and vice versa of certain literary words and expressions has often caused serious problems for the translators who have had insufficient knowledge of the

source or target culture or both of them. For this reason, sometimes literal translations convey meanings which are very far from what the original writer meant.

This study aims to investigate two Persian translations of Golding's *Lord of the Flies* based on Newmark's translation procedures to show that translators can use a variety of strategies or procedures proposed by translation scholars based on the contextual factors of both TL and SL to produce an accurate or communicative rendering of ST.

1.4 Research Questions and Hypotheses

This study tries to provide answers to the following questions:

1. Which procedures have been more used by the translators while translating this novel?
2. In which translation were there more mistranslated items?
3. Does Newmark's framework include all of the procedures used by the translators in this study?
4. Is there any significant relationship between the translators' use of Newmark's procedures?

To answer the above research question, authors propose the following hypotheses:

1. Modulation and transliteration are the most frequent translation strategies applied by the two translators.
2. The two translations are almost the same in terms of mistranslations.
3. Newmark's framework includes all of the procedures used by the translators in this study.
4. There is no significant relationship between the translators' use of Newmark's procedures.

2. Review of the Literature

Newmark's theories and frameworks have been widely applied in the literature for

describing and assessing translations, or for coping with specific translation problems. Bagher (2012) applied the Newmark's framework for exploring the challenges of metaphor translation in the Persian rendering of the Tabari history. His findings revealed that all of the translation strategies used in translation of Tabari history have been already described in Newmark's framework.

Alizade (2010) used Newmark's classification of translation methods to investigate the translation of cultural elements and categories in the Persian translation of "The Great Gatsby". His findings indicated that the translator had applied a mixture of the methods proposed by Newmark to render an accurate and acceptable translation of the source text into Persian.

Sharififar (2000) applied Newmark's model to explore the translation of the Iranian poet, Sepehri's metaphors into English. His findings revealed that Sepehri's metaphors are so complicated that they cannot be easily rendered into English using Newmark's proposed strategies.

Horri (2011) has implemented Newmark's framework in the sacred texts translation to propose a new strategy for rendering Quranic verses, which is a mixture of verbal and semantic translation methods. In Horri's method, translator inserts additional comments in parentheses to refer the readers to exegeses (see also Khazaefar, 2004).

Vahid Dastjerdi, Shahrokhi, & Pirmoradian(2013) also used Newmark's classification of translation procedures to explore the procedures pursued by English translators in rendering metaphors of religious texts from Arabic into English. Their findings revealed that the metaphors

of the Sahifah As-Sajjadiah had been rendered literally into English.

Zekavati and Seddighi (2012) applied Newmark's translation procedures to explore Translatability and Untranslatability of Literary Texts. that translation of high grade literature from Persian into English and English to Persian is possible but to translate all literary figures like rhythm, rhyme, style, proper nouns ,sentences, etc which have cultural and ideological meaning might be done partially and not absolutely(see also Wen-Yan, 2007; Hosseini Maasoum&Davtalab, 2011, Hosseini Maasoum&Moradi, 2011).

Despite the rich literature on the subject, almost no study has considered the applicability of Newmark's procedures simultaneously for both translation and evaluation. This articles aim at filling the gap and accomplishing this mission.

3. Methodology

This paper is an attempt to compare the translation procedures used in two Persian translations of Golding's *Lord of the Flies* by Rafiee (1995) and Mansoori (2004) based on Newmark's translation procedures. To do so, first, some chapters of the English novel were randomly selected, and then, they were compared with their corresponding parts in the Persian translations. Then, comparisons were classified and analyzed.

The research samples were analyzed based on the translation procedures of Newmark (1988) which are as follows:

1. Transference: transferring an SL word to a TL text including transliteration and transcription. Therefore, this word is called a "loan word and therefore, does not change the original form of the SL that is translated into the TL. This procedure is used when there is lack of vocabularies of the TL.

2. Naturalization: adapting the SL word to the normal pronunciation, and then to the

normal morphology of the TL in order to make it familiar to the TL audience. It succeeds transference.

3. Cultural equivalent: replacing a cultural word in the SL with a TL one. Here, translator transfers the relevant cultural equivalents of the SL which is possessed by the TL.

4. Functional equivalent: using a culture-neutral word. This is a common procedure by which a translator tries to explain using a SL word in the TL.

5. Descriptive equivalent: explaining the meaning of the CBT in several words. It differs from functional equivalent. Descriptive equivalent emphasizes more on describing the cultural word.

6. Componential analysis: comparing an SL word with a TL word with a similar meaning that, of course, is not an obvious one-to-one equivalent, by showing first their common and then their differing sense components.

7. Synonymy: it is a near TL equivalent for a SL word in a context, where there may be or may be not a precise equivalent. This procedure is applied for a SL word where there is no one-by-one equivalent, and the word is not important in the text. Because there are many choices of words in the TL, a translator may decide to choose and use one of the equivalent words.

8. Through-translation: the literal translation of common collocations, names of organizations and components of compounds. Other names are: calque or loan translation. It is used only when they are already recognized terms. The clearest example is the names of international organizations which usually consist of universal words that may be transparent for English language.

9. Shifts or transpositions: a change in the grammar from SL to TL.

10. Modulation: reproducing the message of the ST in the TL text in conformity with the current norms of the TL, because of the dissimilar perspectives in the SL and the TL. There are various modulations such as 'part for the whole', 'cause for effect', 'reversal of terms' and 'change of symbols'.

11. Recognized translation: using the officially or the generally accepted translation of any institutional term. This procedure is sometimes inappropriate or poor but the speakers of TL do not reject that.

12. Compensation: compensating loss of meaning in one part of a sentence in another part.

13. Expansion: using more words in the TT for re-expressing an idea or reinforcing the meaning of a ST word because the lack of a concise correspondence in the TL.

14. Paraphrase: explaining the meaning of the CBT much more detailed than that of *descriptive equivalent*.

15. Omission: suppressing elements in the TL text.

16. Couplets: combining two different procedures.

17. Notes, Additions and Glosses are used for supplying additional information in the forms of footnotes, endnotes, glossaries at the end of the text or within the text.

The analyses were made based on a number of the above procedures, and the parallel corpora were investigated and compared in terms of transliteration, shift, synonymy, modulation, addition, omission, as well as mistranslation to find out which procedures were used more by the two translators, and to show the extent of the mistranslated items in the two translations.

4. Analysis and Discussion

English words and expressions with their Persian equivalents were analyzed according to Newmark's model. The results are

summarized in the following figures and tables.

Figure 1: Comparison of Two Persian Translations Based on Newmark's Translation Procedures

As it is shown in figure (1), we can clearly understand that in both Rafiee's translation and Mansoori's translation, 23 (92%) items have been transliterated. In Rafiee's translation, there are 16 (64%) modulated items, and in Mansoori's translation, there are 13 (52%) modulated items. In Rafiee's translation, there are 19 (76%) items of addition, and in Mansoori's translation, there are 11 (44%) items of addition. In Rafiee's translation, there are 22 (88%) items of omission, and in Mansoori's translation, there are four (16%) items of omission.

Regarding the first research question as "Which procedures were more used by the translators for rendering this novel", it was observed that transliteration and omission were the most frequent strategies. These results prove the first research hypothesis regarding the high frequency of transliteration; however, modulation as an efficient method of rendering culture-bound elements does not have a high frequency, which might be due to unawareness of translators of the applicability of this

method, or to the individual translation habits of the translators.

Figure (2) obviously shows that in Rafiee's translation, there are seven (28%) obligatory shifts, 11 (44%) optional shifts and seven (28%) unnecessary shift. On the other hand, in Mansoori's translation, there are seven (28%) obligatory shifts, 10 (40%) optional shifts and eight (32%) items that needed no shift.

As figure (2) indicates, this comparative study showed that concerning transliteration procedure, both translators were similar (92%). Concerning obligatory shifts, again they were similar (28%). However, regarding optional shifts, Rafiee's (44%) has used more shifts than Karimi's (40%). In Rafiee's translation, there are fewer items (28%) which need no shift than Mansoori's translation (32%).

Figure(2) indicates the relatively better performance of Rafiee in rendering the novel, as he has been more successful in detecting the necessity of applying optional shifts. Needless to say, a higher frequency of optional shifts reveals the translator's creativity and his adherence to the TL linguistic and cultural norms.

Figure 2: Comparison of Two Persian Translations based on Newmark's Translation Procedures

Figure 3: Comparison of Two Persian Translations based on Newmark's Translation Procedures

As it is indicated in figure (3), in Rafiee's translation, there are nine (36%) items which can be modified, and in Mansoori's translation, there are 18 (72%) items which can be revised. These statistics reflect the lower rate of using inappropriate equivalents by Rafiee, and reveal the better performance of this translator.

Figure 4: Comparison of Two Persian Translations based on Newmark's Translation Procedures

Regarding the mistranslated parts, figure (4) clearly reveals the fact that in Rafiee's translation, there are six (24%) items mistranslated, and in Mansoori's translation, there are nine (36%) items. The statistics obtained in this part do not refer to inappropriate use of equivalents; rather, they reveal the translation errors which have distorted the ST's elements of meaning. In

this part, Rafiee has outperformed his peer once again. These findings do not confirm the second hypothesis, and reveal the higher frequency of mistranslation in Mansoori's work.

Table 2: Newmark's Procedures Used for Translation of Lord of the Flies

Translation Procedure	The Number of Expressions Found	Translation Strategies Used for Each Expression		Percentage of Translation Strategies Used for Each Expression			
		Rafiee's Translation	Mansoori's Translation	Rafiee's Translation	Mansoori's Translation		
Transliteration	25	23	23	92.0%	92.0%		
Shift	Obligatory	7	7	28.0%	28.0%		
		Optional	25	11	10	44.0%	40.0%
		Not Needed	7	8	28.0%	32.0%	
Synonymy	25	9	18	36.0%	72.0%		
Modulation	25	16	13	64.0%	52.0%		
Addition	25	19	11	76.0%	44.0%		
Omission	25	22	4	88.0%	16.0%		
Mistranslation	25	6	9	24.0%	36.0%		

In order to get a general picture of the results of the present study, table (2) is given to show the comparisons and contrast between the two Persian translations by Rafiee (1995) and Mansoori (2004) based on the Newmark's procedures of translation. The results demonstrated at Table (2) confirm the third hypothesis, as all of the procedures applied by the translators exist in Newmark's framework.

In order to find out if there is any significant relationship between the procedures applied by the two translators in rendering the novel, a Pearson Correlation was run. Results of the correlation coefficient are demonstrated in Table (2).

Table 3: Results for the Correlation Coefficient between the Two Translators' Procedures

N	df	Level of Sig.	Critical Value	Observed Value
14	12	0.05	0.532	0.329*

As Table (3) indicates, the observed correlation value for the pair of data is 0.329(<0.532), which confirms the null hypothesis (hypothesis 4). In other words,

no significant relationship was observed between the frequencies of the different procedures the two translators had applied in their works. These results stand to reason, as our qualitative exploration had revealed the difference of the frequencies used by the two translators. Based on the results in Table (1), the main areas of difference between the two translators are synonymy, omission, and addition.

From among the various translation concepts numerated by Newmark, only “mistranslation” and “translation shifts” can be applied as tools for assessing the performances of the two translators. Despite the non-existence of a significant correlation between the translators’ frequency of procedures, Rafiee has outperformed Mansoori in doing less mistranslations, using more optional shifts, and applying less unnecessary shifts. On the other hand, Mansoori outperformed Rafiee in appropriate use of addition and omission procedures.

5. Conclusion

The present study investigated the translation of 150 English expressions of an English literary masterpiece, *Lord of the flies* by Golding with their Persian equivalents to find out which procedures were used more by the translators while translating this novel and to show in which translation, there were more mistranslated items.

The obtained results of the study revealed the similarity of procedures used by the two translators in general. Yet, each translator revealed his own habitus (internalized translation habits) in using various procedures. In this regard, each translator outperformed his peer in fulfilling some aspects of translation.

Results concerning synonymy showed that Mansoori’s translation needs more

modification than Rafiee’s translation in order to be more communicative. Further, the results showed that Mansoori’s translation based on Newmark’s procedure of “addition”, is more communicative than Rafiee’s translation. Moreover, it was observed that Rafiee’s translation has ignored translating some items more than Mansoori’s, and in this way it is not considered as a complete translation for the original text.

Our findings are in line with those obtained by Bagher (2012) and Alizade (2010). In other words, based on the results of this study, it was shown that Newmark’s procedures are nearly comprehensive and worked well for assessing the translation of a literary work. Therefore, the researchers hope that this study has clarified the applicability of the translation procedures proposed by Newmark.

The present study has implications for translators, translation instructors, and translation critics. Translators can apply Newmark’s procedures (such as transliteration, shift, addition, and omission) for dealing with different translation problems during the process of translation. Transliteration is a useful method for rendering proper names. Addition, omission, and shifts are inevitable in translation as languages have different potentials in expressing elements of meaning.

On the other hand, Translation instructors can train their learners to use Newmark’s procedures effectively and in appropriate situations. For example, transliteration cannot be used in rendering idioms and metaphorical expressions, as these elements are culture-bound elements. Finally, translation critics can use Newmark’s procedures for evaluating translations and comparing them with each other. As mentioned earlier, a translator’s

capability of applying shifts indicates his translation ability to a large extent. In this regard, low level translators even fail to apply obligatory shifts, or to recognize unnecessary ones. Intermediate level translators apply obligatory shifts but they may fail to apply optional shifts in an appropriate manner. On the other hand, high level translators can be recognized by their ability of applying optional translation shifts in appropriate situations.

Like any other study, the present research is limited in some aspects. The following suggestions are proposed for the translators who are interested in literary translation for further study:

1. Literary translators are advised to pay more attention to the translation of cultural specific items while translating so that they can produce a comprehensible and communicative translation for the target readers.
2. Literary translators are also recommended to use Newmark's translation procedures while translating, to produce an accurate translation with no mistake or with the least amount of possible mistakes.
3. It seems extremely appropriate to do a study on translation of this novel based on Newmark's model of meaning.
4. Translation of this novel can be investigated in the context of Critical Discourse Analysis to measure the effect of various translation procedures and strategies.
5. The present study utilized an English-Persian parallel corpus. Other researchers are recommended to focus on the other pairs of languages (e.g. French-Persian).
6. This case study was focused on the translation of one literary work. The same framework can be implemented for studying the translation of other literary works.

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